

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.483 Max: 62.614	1448 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1953-56	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 301
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DEFINITION wall west of SU 1424	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash		
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells		
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass				

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1390, 1424,
Is covered by: 1412	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS

DESCRIPTION located near the southern limit of Area B, to the west of center
 Position within sector: positioned south of wall 1390, west of SU 1424
 Shape: rectangular

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight	
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping	
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular	
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
Observations:	

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: runs North to South

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions: —

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type —

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

L=161cm W=45cm H= east=20cm west=20cm

Description:

wall extends south from wall 1390 and is comprised of middle sized stones

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Creates a new room south of wall 1390. Southern extent of the wall is no longer present, possibly due to previous excavation, additionally trajectory of the wall appears to go over wt 1431 and may have been removed at that point.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	S. Jan	on	26.7.2011
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